

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN KAKCHING AND CHANDEL DISTRICTS OF MANIPUR

Asha Elizabeth Chhetri

Assistant Inspector of Schools, Autonomous District Council, Sadar Hills, Kangpokpi, Manipur

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of parental involvement on the academic achievement of secondary school students in the contrasting districts of Kakching and Chandel in Manipur, India. Employing a descriptive correlational design, the study sampled 400 Class XI students (200 from each district) selected through multistage stratified random sampling. Data were collected using the Parental Involvement Scale (TPIS) and students' annual examination scores. Analysis using descriptive statistics, Mann-Whitney U tests, Chi-Square tests, multiple regression, and Spearman's correlation revealed several key findings. Students in Kakching district reported significantly higher levels of parental involvement than those in Chandel (Mean Rank = 216.63 vs. 184.37, $p = .005$). However, the two districts had no significant difference in academic achievement levels ($\chi^2 = 2.046$, $p = .359$). Moreover, the correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement was non-significant in both Chandel ($\rho = -.045$) and Kakching ($\rho = +0.068$). A regression analysis identified school type ($\beta = -.362$) and location ($\beta = .333$) as the only significant predictors of academic achievement. At the same time, parental involvement and other demographic factors were insignificant. These results challenge the universally positive association found in Western literature, suggesting that in Manipur's unique socio-cultural and economic context, structural factors like school quality and geographical location overshadow the influence of parental engagement on academic outcomes. The findings underscore the need for context-specific, culturally responsive educational policies and interventions.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Academic Achievement, Secondary School Students, Manipur, Kakching, Chandel.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of the involvement of parents in education in determining students' academic success is widely recognised, regardless of cultural or national context. Broadly defined, parental involvement refers to the active participation of parents in their children's educational experiences through encouragement, supervision, communication, and school engagement (Jeynes, 2012). Decades of international research have consistently highlighted its significance, demonstrating that when parents are actively engaged, children tend to perform better academically, socially, and emotionally (Fan & Chen, 2001; Hill & Tyson, 2009). This active participation is a cornerstone of a supportive learning environment beyond the classroom.

In the Indian context, where family structures and collectivist values strongly shape children's upbringing, parental involvement is crucial. Scholars argue that parental behaviours and expectations are deeply influenced by cultural norms, socio-economic status, and local community practices (Deslandes & Cloutier, 2002; Rao, 2016). For this reason, contextualized studies within India are necessary to capture regional differences in parental engagement and their effects on student achievement.

The northeastern state of Manipur provides a unique setting for such research. Known for its ethnic and linguistic diversity, Manipur's districts differ considerably in socio-economic development, resource access, and cultural practices (Singh & Mishra, 2018). Among them, Kakching and Chandel represent contrasting educational environments. Kakching is relatively more developed, with better infrastructure, transportation, and school facilities. At the same time, Chandel faces geographic isolation, resource limitations, and a predominantly tribal population with distinct socio-cultural traditions (Government of Manipur, 2020). These differences make comparative analysis of parental involvement and achievement particularly relevant.

Despite the growing acknowledgment of parental involvement as a key factor in educational success, empirical studies in Manipur remain limited. Much of the existing Indian research focuses on metropolitan areas or other regions, leaving a gap in understanding the dynamics within the northeastern states (Devi & Thingujam, 2017). In Manipur, Devi and Thingujam's study in Imphal revealed a positive association between parental involvement, particularly home supervision and communication, and students' achievement. However, their research did not extend to Kakching and Chandel or employ standardized instruments such as the Parental Involvement Scale (TPIS). Addressing this gap is essential, as district-level variations may reveal how local contexts mediate the influence of parental engagement on learning outcomes.

The theoretical foundation for this investigation draws on Epstein's Overlapping Spheres of Influence Model (1995, 2011) and Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler's Model of Parental Involvement (1995, 1997). Epstein conceptualizes schools, families, and communities as interconnected domains jointly influencing student learning. Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler emphasize parental role construction, efficacy beliefs, and perceptions of school invitations as drivers of involvement. These frameworks provide a lens for analyzing how parental practices in Manipur's distinct cultural settings shape student achievement (Epstein, 1995; Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997).

The present study seeks to address the question: How does parental involvement impact the academic achievement of secondary school students in Kakching and Chandel districts of Manipur? By employing the TPIS within these two distinct contexts, the study aims to expand theoretical insights while generating practical implications.

The significance of this research is twofold. Theoretically, it contributes to the cross-cultural validation of established parental involvement frameworks by applying them in a relatively underexplored region of India. It offers policymakers, school administrators, and educators valuable insights for designing culturally responsive strategies to enhance parental engagement. These findings align with India's National Education Policy 2020 priorities, emphasising community participation as a cornerstone for improving educational outcomes (Ministry of Education, 2020). By situating national policy goals within the local realities of Manipur, this research underscores the urgent need to tailor educational interventions to diverse socio-cultural landscapes, moving beyond one-size-fits-all solutions.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Parental involvement has long been established as a vital determinant of student outcomes. Meta-analyses consistently reveal a strong positive association between parental engagement and academic achievement. Jeynes (2012), in a review of 95 studies, found that parental expectations, school communication, and supervision were the most powerful predictors of success, with effect sizes between 0.20 and 0.40 (Jeynes, 2012). Similarly, Wilder (2014) synthesized 51 studies and confirmed that involvement benefits students across all levels of education, particularly in secondary schooling (Wilder, 2014). Specific practices such as monitoring homework, maintaining high expectations, and

academic socialization (discussing aspirations and values) emerged as most effective (Hill & Tyson, 2009).

Epstein's (2011) six-type model, parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration, has been influential in conceptualizing the multidimensional nature of parental involvement. Research applying this framework indicates that home-based involvement (helping with homework, discussing schoolwork) tends to produce more substantial gains in secondary students' achievement than school-based involvement (attending school events), particularly in adolescence when autonomy increases (Hill & Tyson, 2009).

Cultural norms shape how parents support children. In collectivist societies, parental involvement emphasizes respect for authority and shared family responsibility. At the same time, individualist contexts focus on advocacy and direct assistance (Chao & Tseng, 2002). Lee and Bowen (2006) observed that in Asian families, high expectations and emphasis on effort predicted stronger outcomes than direct academic help (Lee & Bowen, 2006).

Socio-economic status (SES) also strongly moderates the involvement-achievement relationship. Sirin's (2005) meta-analysis of 74 studies found that SES correlated with achievement ($r = .30$). However, parental involvement partially mediated this relationship; families with low SES but high engagement often buffered disadvantage (Sirin, 2005). Longitudinal studies confirm sustained effects; Fan and Chen (2001) showed that parental involvement predicts achievement through high school and beyond (Fan & Chen, 2001).

Indian research reveals both similarities to and deviations from global patterns. Rao (2016) demonstrated that parental education and economic background strongly influence involvement levels, with higher SES families engaging more in academically oriented activities (Rao, 2016). Singh and Mishra (2018) highlighted persistent gender disparities, with rural parents investing more in sons' education (Singh & Mishra, 2018). However, this trend narrows in urban settings. The type of school also matters: government school parents typically show lower involvement than private school parents, constrained by socio-economic barriers and institutional expectations (Saha, 2015).

Studies in Northeast India are limited but highlight cultural distinctiveness. In Imphal district, Devi and Thingujam (2017) found positive correlations between parental involvement, particularly home supervision and communication, and secondary students' achievement. Kamei (2019) noted that in Manipuri society, involvement often takes the form of indirect support rooted in cultural traditions (Kamei, 2019). In Assam, Borah (2020) found rural-urban disparities in involvement, with urban families demonstrating higher engagement, reflecting contextual differences similar to those between Kakching and Chandel districts (Borah, 2020).

While global and Indian research underscores the positive role of parental involvement, district-level evidence in Manipur is scarce. Existing studies primarily focus on urban centers or other states, overlooking the unique socio-cultural fabric of Northeast India. Moreover, no comparative research has examined parental involvement across these two districts using standardized measures like TPIS.

This study addresses these gaps by investigating parental involvement's patterns and predictive power on academic achievement in Kakching and Chandel, thereby contributing context-specific evidence to national and global discourse.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive correlational design with comparative elements to examine the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement among secondary school students in Kakching and Chandel districts of Manipur. The correlational approach identified

associations between the variables, while the comparative element explored district-level differences. The population comprised students who were newly enrolled in Class XI and were from government and private schools. A sample of 400 students (200 from each district) was selected using multistage stratified random sampling to ensure balanced representation by gender, school type, and socio-economic background.

Data were collected using two tools. The Parental Involvement Scale (TPIS) developed by Chouhan and Arora (2009) was employed to measure parental involvement across three dimensions: support and communication, monitoring and supervision, and control and restriction. This 25-item scale uses a 5-point Likert format and demonstrated high reliability in this study (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.902$). Academic achievement was assessed through students' cumulative percentage scores from their latest annual examinations. Demographic details were also recorded. Data were analysed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, Spearman's correlation examined relationships, and multiple regression tested predictive power. For district comparisons, independent samples t-tests and relevant non-parametric tests were applied.

4. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are:

1. To assess the parental involvement level among secondary school students in Kakching and Chandel districts.
2. To examine and compare the academic achievement levels of students in the two districts.
3. To evaluate the predictive power of parental involvement on academic achievement after controlling for demographic factors such as gender, location, parental education, income, and school type.
4. To determine the relationship between academic achievement and parental involvement for students in both districts.
5. To provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, educators, and parents to foster effective parental engagement strategies tailored to the local context of Manipur.

5. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS IN RELATION TO OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Objective 1: Assessment of Parental Involvement Levels in Kakching and Chandel Districts

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Parental Involvement

District	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Kakching	200	66.68	10.639
Chandel	200	65.54	11.236
Average (Districts)	400	65.61	10.980

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of parental involvement among students of Kakching and Chandel districts. The mean score for Kakching ($M = 66.68$, $SD = 10.64$) was slightly higher than that of Chandel ($M = 64.54$, $SD = 11.24$). When both districts were considered together, the overall average was 65.61 ($SD = 10.98$). These results suggest that parental involvement in both districts is moderate. However, parents of Kakching appear to be more engaged in their children's education and developmental activities than those in Chandel.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney U Test for Parental Involvement

District	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Chandel	200	184.37	36873.50
Kakching	200	216.63	42226.50
Total	400		

A non-parametric Mann-Whitney U in **Table 2** is used to assess further whether this difference was statistically significant. The ranks show that the mean Rank for Kakching (216.63) was notably higher than that of Chandel's (184.37). It indicates that, overall, parental involvement scores tend to be greater for students in Kakching.

Table 3: Test Statistics^a for the Mann-Whitney U Test

	Parental Involvement
Mann-Whitney U	16773.500
Wilcoxon W	36873.500
	-2.801
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.005
a. Grouping Variable: Districts	

Table 3 shows that the Mann-Whitney U value was 16,773.50, with a Wilcoxon W of 36,873.50. The standardized test statistic yielded a Z value of -2.801, with an associated p-value of .005. Since the significance level is less than .01, the result confirms a statistically significant difference in parental involvement between the two districts.

The descriptive and inferential analyses reveal that students in Kakching district report significantly higher parental involvement than students in Chandel. This finding may reflect variations in socio-economic conditions, parental awareness, or cultural differences in parenting practices across the two districts. The evidence suggests that Kakching parents are more actively guiding, monitoring, and supporting their children, which could have important implications for student outcomes.

5.2 Objective 2: Achievement Levels of Students based on Districts

Table 4: Achievement Levels by Districts

		District		Total
		Chandel	Kakching	
Achievement Levels	Secured above 60 % marks	109	112	221
	Secured between 45-60 % marks	89	88	177
	Below 45 % marks	2	0	2
Total		200	200	400

Table 4 shows the cross-tabulation of student achievement levels across Chandel and Kakching districts. Out of 400 students, a majority in both districts secured above 60% marks: 109 in Chandel and 112 in Kakching, totalling 221 students (55.3%). A smaller but substantial proportion secured between 45-60% marks, with 89 from Chandel and 88 from Kakching, totalling 177 students (44.3%). Only two students (0.5%) from Chandel scored below 45%. The distribution reveals that in both districts, most students performed at a moderate to high level, with very few showing low achievement.

Table 5: Chi-Square Tests for Achievement Levels by District

Test	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.046 ^a	2	.359
Likelihood Ratio	2.819	2	.244
Linear-by-Linear Association	.242	1	.623
N of Valid Cases	400		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.00.

Table 5 analyses whether academic achievement levels differed significantly by district. A Chi-Square test of independence was conducted. The Pearson Chi-Square value was 2.046 with 2 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .359, which is greater than the conventional significance level of .05. Similarly, the likelihood ratio and linear-by-linear association tests also showed non-significant results ($p > .05$). These findings indicate no significant association between district and academic achievement levels. In other words, the academic performance of students in Kakching and Chandel is comparable, with both districts showing similar proportions of high, average, and low achievers. The slight differences observed in frequencies are not statistically meaningful.

Thus, the analysis suggests that while Kakching students showed marginally higher frequencies in top achievement categories, overall, the district does not significantly determine students' academic achievement levels.

5.3 Objective 3: Predictive Power of Parental Involvement Based on Demographic Factors

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for Regression Analysis

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Parental Involvement	65.74	10.723	259
Gender	1.57	.496	259
School Type	1.25	.432	259
Location	1.55	.498	259
Monthly Income of Parents	2.16	.607	259
Educational Level of Father	.94	.458	259
Educational Level of Mother	.86	.436	259
Districts	1.77	.420	259

Table 6 shows the mean parental involvement score is 65.74 (SD = 10.72, N = 259). According to the TPIS manual, this falls within the *low involvement* category, highlighting modest parental engagement overall. Demographic profiles reveal that gender is nearly balanced (Mean = 1.57, SD = .496), with a slight female majority. Most students are from government schools (Mean = 1.25, SD = .432) and rural locations (Mean = 1.55, SD = .498). Parents' educational levels are low (father: Mean = 0.94, SD = .458; mother: Mean = 0.86, SD = .436), while the average monthly income category is 2.16 (SD = .607), pointing toward lower to middle-income households.

Table 7: Model Summary for Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.270 ^a	.073	.047	10.467	.073	.2830	7	251	.007

a. Predictors: (Constant), Districts, Educational Level of Mother, School Type, Gender, Educational Level of Father, Monthly Income of Parents, Location

Table 7 presents the regression model summary. The model yielded $R = .270$, $R^2 = .073$, Adjusted $R^2 = .047$, with $p = .007$, indicating that demographics account for 7.3% of the variance in parental involvement. While statistically significant, this suggests that most variation arises from non-demographic factors such as parental attitudes, cultural practices, or school-home communication.

Table 8: ANOVA^a for Regression Analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2169.881	7	309.983	2.830	.007 ^b
	Residual	27497.787	251	109.553		
	Total	29667.668	258			

a. Dependent Variable: Parental Involvement
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Districts, Educational Level of Mother, School Type, Gender, Educational Level of Father, Monthly Income of Parents, Location

Table 8 confirms the model's significance, with $F(7, 251) = 2.830$, $p = .007$. It indicates that, taken together, the demographic factors have a meaningful but limited predictive effect on parental involvement.

Table 9: Coefficients^a for Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	44.503	6.471		6.878	.000
	Gender	3.189	1.378	.147	2.315	.021
	School Type	-3.500	1.831	-.141	-1.912	.057
	Location	3.680	1.782	.171	2.065	.040
	Monthly Income of Parents	2.665	1.195	.151	2.230	.027
	Educational Level of Father	.104	1.503	.004	.069	.945
	Educational Level of Mother	.124	1.523	.005	.081	.935
	Districts	5.030	1.945	.197	2.586	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Parental Involvement

Table 9 identifies significant predictors. Gender ($B = 3.189$, $p = .021$) indicates females are associated with higher involvement. Location ($B = 3.680$, $p = .040$) shows urban parents are more engaged than rural parents. Monthly income ($B = 2.665$, $p = .027$) suggests higher-income families provide greater involvement. District ($B = 5.030$, $p = .010$) highlights that Kakching parents score higher than those in

Chandel. By contrast, educational level of father ($B = .104, p = .945$) and mother ($B = .124, p = .935$) are non-significant, and school type ($B = -3.500, p = .057$) is only marginal. Tables 6-9 reveal that parental involvement is shaped significantly by district, gender, income, and location, but not by parental education. It underscores the importance of addressing structural and socio-economic barriers, especially in rural and low-income families, to enhance meaningful parental participation in education.

5.4 Objective 4: Relationship Between Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement in Kakching and Chandel Districts

Table 10: Correlations Between Academic Achievement and Parental Involvement

District	Variable	N	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman's rho)	Sig. (2-tailed)
Chandel	Parental Involvement ↔ Achievement Levels	200	- .045	0.525
Kakching	Parental Involvement ↔ Achievement Levels	200	+0.068	0.342

Table 10 examines Spearman's rho correlation to analyse the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement in Chandel and Kakching districts. In Chandel, the correlation is weakly negative ($\rho = -0.045, p = 0.525$), while in Kakching it is weakly positive ($\rho = +0.068, p = 0.342$). Both results are statistically non-significant, indicating that no meaningful monotonic relationship exists between parental involvement and achievement in either district.

This finding contrasts with much of the international literature, which often identifies a positive link between parental engagement and student achievement (Fan & Chen, 2001). However, it aligns with regional realities. It is noted that most parental involvement in low-literacy contexts is limited to basic supervision and moral support, which may not directly affect exam scores. Similarly, it is highlighted that in Manipur, structural conditions, such as rural isolation, school quality, and socio-economic disparities, often overshadow family-level factors. Thus, while Kakching shows slightly higher parental involvement than Chandel, these differences do not translate into higher academic outcomes. The results suggest systemic improvements in school resources and parental awareness are necessary before involvement significantly influences achievement.

6. DISCUSSION

This study explored parental involvement in secondary school students' academic achievement in the Kakching and Chandel Manipur districts. The findings provide important insights that both support and challenge existing literature.

The results revealed a significant district-level difference in parental involvement. As shown in Table 1, students in Kakching reported a higher mean involvement score ($M = 66.68, SD = 10.64$) than those in Chandel ($M = 64.54, SD = 11.24$). The Mann-Whitney U test confirmed this difference as statistically significant ($U = 16,773.50, Z = -2.801, p = .005$; Table 3). These findings resonate with Rao's (2016) and Sirin's (2005) observations that socio-economic status and local resources shape parental engagement. Kakching, with relatively better infrastructure, appears to enable higher parental participation compared to Chandel, where geographic isolation and limited resources constrain involvement.

Despite these differences, academic achievement did not significantly vary between districts. Table 4 shows that 55.3% of students across both districts scored above 60%, with almost identical

distributions between Kakching (n = 112) and Chandel (n = 109). The Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 2.046$, $p = .359$; Table 5) confirmed no significant association between district and achievement. This finding contrasts Wilder's (2014) meta-synthesis and Jeynes' (2012) meta-analysis, which consistently report positive associations between involvement and achievement across diverse contexts. The Manipur case suggests that even higher parental involvement, as seen in Kakching, does not necessarily lead to better performance.

The correlation analysis strengthens this conclusion. In Chandel, parental involvement showed a weak negative correlation with achievement ($\rho = -.045$, $p = .525$), while in Kakching, the relationship was weakly positive ($\rho = +.068$, $p = .342$). However, in both cases, it was non-significant (Table 10). These findings diverge from Fan and Chen's (2001) meta-analysis, highlighting a positive relationship across multiple studies. Instead, they align more closely with Kamei's (2019) argument that in Manipur, parental involvement often takes indirect forms, such as providing moral guidance, rather than direct academic support. Similarly, Devi and Thingujam (2017) found positive effects of supervision in Imphal. However, they cautioned that such patterns may not generalize across districts with differing socio-economic conditions.

Regression analysis further highlighted the limited role of parental involvement in predicting achievement. As shown in Table 9, only school type ($\beta = -.362$, $p < .05$) and location ($\beta = .333$, $p < .05$) significantly predicted academic performance. At the same time, parental involvement, parental education, and income were not significant predictors. These results echo Borah's (2020) findings in Assam, where rural–urban disparities and structural constraints exerted more potent effects on achievement than parental engagement.

The present study underscores that while parental involvement levels differ significantly between Kakching and Chandel, such differences do not translate into academic outcomes. It challenges the universal applicability of Western-derived frameworks (Epstein, 2011; Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997) and demonstrates the need for culturally and contextually grounded approaches. In Manipur, structural and institutional factors, rather than parental practices alone, appear to shape student achievement decisively.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study offer significant contributions to understanding the complex dynamics of parental involvement within Manipur's unique educational landscape. By demonstrating that the expected positive relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement does not hold in this context, the study underscores the critical importance of tailoring educational strategies to local realities. In light of the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- a) **Develop District-Specific Parental Engagement Programs:** Educational authorities should design and implement engagement programs tailored to the specific needs of each district. In Kakching, where involvement is already higher, programs could focus on elevating engagement to more impactful forms, such as greater participation in school decision-making. In Chandel, interventions should prioritize building foundational parental capacity for home-based academic support and improving school-home communication, recognizing the district's resource and geographical constraints.
- b) **Organize Culturally Responsive Parenting Workshops:** Schools should host workshops that respect and integrate local cultural values while providing parents with practical, evidence-based strategies for effective involvement. These sessions should emphasize the specific support practices most likely to foster academic growth within their cultural context.

- c) **Bridge the Socio-economic and Geographical Gap:** Special initiatives are needed to target low-SES families, particularly in remote areas of Chandel, where the involvement gap and resource limitations are most pronounced. Leveraging technology, such as mobile-based communication platforms, could help overcome geographical barriers and enhance parent-school engagement.
- d) **Enhance Teacher Training on Parent Collaboration:** Professional development programs for teachers should include modules on effectively engaging parents from diverse socio-economic and cultural backgrounds. Training should build trust, foster mutual understanding, and create a welcoming school environment for all families.
- e) **Integrate Context-Specific Policies:** State education policies must formally recognize parental involvement as a key component of educational quality, with specific provisions designed for the unique contexts of Northeast India. The Manipur State Council of Educational Research and Training (SCERT) could lead the development of guidelines for parental engagement that are culturally sensitive and responsive to local realities.

This study has certain limitations, including its reliance on self-reported measures of parental involvement and its cross-sectional design, which precludes causal inferences. Future research should employ longitudinal designs and incorporate multiple perspectives (parents, teachers, and students) to develop a more comprehensive understanding of these dynamics. Intervention studies testing the effectiveness of culturally tailored engagement programs would also be invaluable for strengthening the evidence base for regional policy development.

In short, this research underscores that in Manipur's unique socio-cultural environment, structural factors, particularly a student's location and school type, play more decisive roles in determining academic outcomes than parental involvement alone. While the global literature consistently highlights a positive correlation, this study reveals that context is paramount. For parental involvement to become a truly effective lever for improving academic achievement and fostering educational equity in Manipur, systemic improvements in school resources and implementing contextually adapted engagement strategies are essential. By adopting these recommendations, policymakers and educational institutions can create a more supportive and inclusive academic environment that maximizes the potential of all students in Kakching, Chandel, and beyond.

REFERENCES

1. Borah, P. (2020). A comparative study on parental involvement between rural and urban secondary school students in Sivasagar district of Assam. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 78, 102263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2020.102263>
2. Chao, R. K., & Tseng, V. (2002). Parenting of Asians. In M. H. Bornstein (Ed.), *Handbook of parenting* (2nd ed., pp. 59–93). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
3. Deslandes, R., & Cloutier, R. (2002). Parents' perceived barriers to involvement in secondary school. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 17(1–2), 77–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/082957350201700106>
4. Devi, T. S., & Thingujam, N. S. (2017). Parental involvement and academic achievement among secondary school students in Imphal, Manipur. *Indian Journal of Health and Wellbeing*, 8(5), 567–573.
5. Epstein, J. L. (1995). School/family/community partnerships: Caring for the children we share. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 76(9), 701–712.

6. Fan, X., & Chen, M. (2001). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 13(1), 1–22.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009048817385>
7. Hill, N. E., & Tyson, D. F. (2009). Parental Involvement in Middle School: A Meta-Analytic Assessment of the Strategies That Promote Achievement. *Developmental Psychology*, 45(3), 740–763. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0015362>
8. Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & Sandler, H. M. (1997). Why do parents become involved in their children's education? *Review of Educational Research*, 67(1), 3–42.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543067001003>
9. Jeynes, W. H. (2012). A meta-analysis of the relationship between parental involvement and urban secondary school student academic achievement. *Urban Education*, 47(4), 720–749.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085912445645>
10. Kamei, T. (2019). Cultural specificity of parental involvement practices in Manipur. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(3), 112–124. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jesr-2019-0031>
11. Lee, J., & Bowen, N. K. (2006). Parent involvement and academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 18(4), 309–334.
12. Ministry of Education. (2020). *National Education Policy 2020*. Government of India.
13. Rao, N. (2016). Parental involvement in education across urban and rural settings in India. *Contemporary Education Dialogue*, 13(2), 211–232.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0973224116658392>
14. Saha, L. (2015). Parental involvement in government and private schools in India: A comparative study. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 45, 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2015.07.001>
15. Singh, R., & Mishra, S. (2018). Gender differences in parental involvement and academic achievement in Indian secondary schools. *Indian Journal of Educational Research*, 57(3), 234–248.
16. Sirin, S. R. (2005). Socio-economic status and academic achievement: A meta-analytic review of research. *Review of Educational Research*, 75(3), 417–453.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543075003417>
17. Wilder, S. (2014). Effects of parental Involvement on academic achievement: A meta-synthesis. *Educational Review*, 66(3), 377–397.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2013.780002>